

Extinction Contexts Fail to Transfer Control: Implications for Conditioned Inhibition and Occasion-Setting Accounts of Renewal

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The renewal effect is often explained as a side effect of the extinction context acting as a negative occasion setter. Four experiments tested whether extinction contexts show the selective-transfer property of occasion setters. Experiments 1–3 used a predictive judgment task where participants rated the probability of certain foods (cues) producing gastric malaise (outcomes) in different restaurants (con-texts). Experiment 4 used a behavioral suppression task where sensor lights (cues) served as signals to suppress firing responses in certain galaxies (contexts). All 4 (Experiments 1–4) addressed whether a potentially negative occasion-setting context transferred its modulatory power to an extinguished (presumably occasion set) target in the test phase of an ABC renewal design. Experiments 2–4 further assessed the possibility that the extinction context acts as a conditioned inhibitor by testing a simple excitator on a context where extinction occurred. Neither selective (occasion-setting) nor nonselective transfer (conditioned inhibition) was demonstrated. Implications for theories of renewal and occasion-setting are discussed.

Keywords: extinction, contexts, renewal, occasion-setting, conditioned inhibition

When a neutral stimulus is paired with one which elicits some unconditioned response (US) it becomes a conditioned stimulus (CS); that is, it comes to elicit a related response as a function of those pairings. When the CS is then presented without the US, extinction occurs. The response to the CS declines and eventually disappears. Additionally, during extinction, the context becomes important. The present article investigates negative-occasion-

setting mechanisms by which contexts might operate during extinction.

The importance of the context in extinction is especially apparent in the renewal effect. Renewal refers to the recovery of the conditioned response (CR) when the CS is tested out of the context where extinction occurred. The most robust form of renewal is “ABA” renewal (e.g., Thomas, Larsen, & Ayres, 2003). Here, the CS is conditioned in a given context (A), extinguished in a different one (B), and tested back in A (e.g., Bouton & Bolles, 1979). Renewal, however, also occurs when each phase takes place in a different context (ABC renewal; e.g., Denniston, Chang, & Miller, 2003) or when there is a single context change before testing (AAB renewal; e.g., Bouton & Ricker, 1994; Tamai & Nakajima, 2000). In these forms of renewal, no US is presented in the test context and the effect cannot be explained through context-US excitatory associations as could be expected according to the Rescorla-Wagner (Rescorla & Wagner, 1972) model.

A way to explain all forms of renewal within the Rescorla-Wagner framework is by assuming that the absence of the expected US during extinction results in the extinction context acquiring conditioned inhibitory properties. Thus, the extinction context may directly suppress the representation or expectation of the outcome. Renewal would appear because the subject is free from the inhibition exerted by the extinction context on test. Moreover, the inhibition accrued to the context could protect the CS from losing associative strength (Rescorla, 2003; Soltysik,

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Wolfe, Nicholas, Wilson, & Garcia-Sanchez, 1983), ensuring that it is preserved and manifested at test.

Support for this account is mixed, suggesting that other mechanisms are also at work. Some studies have shown conditioned inhibition to the extinction context (Cunningham, 1979; Glautier, Elgueta, & Nelson, 2013; Polack, Laborda, & Miller, 2012; see also Miller, Laborda, & Polack, 2020, for findings that might indicate contextual inhibition after extinction), whereas others have not (e.g., Baker, McNally, & Richardson, 2012; Bouton & King, 1983; Bouton & Swartzentruber, 1986, 1989; Grahame, Hallam, Geier, & Miller, 1990; Nelson et al., 2011). Just as context-US *excitatory* associations cannot explain all forms of renewal, demonstrations of the absence of contextual conditioned inhibition after extinction prevent *inhibitory* context-US associations from explaining all cases of renewal. Therefore, a full account of this effect should not depend on direct context-outcome associations, unless additional assumptions are incorporated to explain the effect in their absence.

A widely cited account of renewal has been suggested by Bouton (e.g., Bouton, 1993, 2004). His approach to extinction and renewal is represented in Figure 1 (first presented in Bouton & Nelson, 1994; see also Bouton, 1994). The model assumes that a relatively context-independent excitatory association develops between the CS and the US during conditioning (arrow in Figure 1). Then, extinction produces new, inhibitory learning that contradicts the previous association of the CS (blocked line in Figure 1). Describing such associations as meanings, interference might cause the animal to pay attention to the context as a way to disambiguate the meaning of the CS (Bouton, 1997; Nelson, Fabiano, & Lamoureux, 2018; Rosas, Callejas-Aguilera, Ramos-Álvarez, & Abad, 2006). The result is that inhibition of the outcome representation becomes dependent on the presence of both the stimulus and the context, so that in the absence of the extinction context at test, the inhibitory link will not be activated and renewal would be observed. That mechanism is shown by the convergence of input from the CS and the extinction context on what Bouton (1993) described as an Estes (1976)-type “AND” gate that requires input from both for activation.

The role of context in Bouton’s model has been described as an occasion-setting mechanism (e.g., Bouton, 1993, 2004, see also Bouton & Nelson, 1994; Nelson & Bouton, 1997). Whereas conventional CSs are stimuli that predict the presence of a given outcome, occasion setters inform on *whether* (Bouton, 1997) another stimulus is going to be followed by the outcome (positive occasion setters), or not (negative occasion setters). In Bouton’s

Figure 1. Bouton’s (1993) model of extinction. The arrow represents an excitatory association; the blocked line represents an inhibitory association. The inhibition depends upon convergence of input from the conditioned stimulus (CS) and the context on an “AND” gate (Estes, 1976) for expression. US = unconditioned response.

approach to extinction, the extinction context is assumed to act as a negative occasion setter, informing that the CS is not going to be reinforced.

The literature on occasion-setting is thoroughly reviewed elsewhere (Fraser & Holland, 2019; Holland, 1992; Swartzentruber, 1995). Briefly, negative occasion-setting is typically obtained in serial feature-negative (FN) discrimination training. In such training, a target CS is reinforced (T+) unless preceded by another stimulus that serves as the negative feature (F→T-), or negative occasion setter. Occasion-setting is also obtained with simultaneous presentations of the feature and target stimuli, but in those cases the feature is less salient than the target (e.g., Holland, 1989a).

Conditioning and extinction in a renewal design could be viewed as a FN discrimination, where the CS is reinforced unless accompanied by the extinction context, which serves as the negative feature. Moreover, given the punctate nature of the CS and the more continuous presence of the context, presentation of the CS within the extinction context would resemble serial presentation of the stimuli. According to this view, any context that has had extinction within it can be regarded as a negative occasion setter, and any extinguished stimulus can be considered to have been trained as an occasion-setting target.

A recent review by Trask, Thrailkill, and Bouton (2017) concluded that Pavlovian extinction results in contexts functioning as occasion setters. Closer examination, however, reveals that the evidence may not be as strong as has been assumed; critical questions regarding this parallelism have yet to be answered. The present study reviews some of these questions and includes four experiments that assessed whether contexts accomplish one of the commonly referred characteristics of occasion setters: their ability to modulate responding to stimuli trained in different discriminations.

One of the hallmarks of occasion setters is that their modulatory power is not lost after they are reinforced or extinguished. For example, in an appetitive procedure with rats, Nelson and Bouton (1997) trained a light as a negative occasion setter with a tone in a serial FN discrimination (T+/L→T-). After the discrimination was acquired, subsequent reinforcement of the light on its own did not abolish its ability to suppress responding to the tone (see also Baeyens, Vansteenwegen, Hermans, Vervliet, & Eelen, 2001; Holland, 1984, 1989a, 1991; Nelson & Bouton, 1997).

It is here that extinction contexts begin to differ from occasion setters. For instance, there is evidence that following extinction, presentations of the US in the extinction context “reinstate” the CR when the CS is tested in that context (Bouton & Peck, 1989). Ostensibly, from an occasion-setting perspective such a treatment should leave the contexts’ negative-occasion-setting abilities intact. Bouton (1993) preserves the occasion-setting interpretation in this situation by assuming that the associations with the outcome acquired during the US presentations produce a change in the context. That is, the context is no longer the same contextual stimulus that had acquired occasion-setting abilities during extinction. However, as discussed earlier, occasion setters formed by discrete stimuli do not have that characteristic; reinforcement does not transform them into a different stimulus with respect to their occasion-setting abilities.

A second phenomenon widely reported in the literature on occasion-setting is selective transfer. Occasion setters do not rou-

tinely transfer their modulatory properties to other CSs unless those CSs have been trained as targets in a similar occasion-setting discrimination (e.g., Baeyens et al., 2001; Bonardi & Hall, 1994; Davidson & Rescorla, 1986; Holland, 1986; Holland, 1989b; Lamarre & Holland, 1987; Rescorla, 1985). That is, occasion setters best affect stimuli that have themselves been occasion set.

Lamarre and Holland (1987), for example, gave rats separate pairings of a tone and a noise with a shock (T+, N+). Then, the tone continued to be reinforced but serial presentations of a houselight and the tone were not (T+, H→T-), presumably establishing the houselight as a negative occasion setter. The groups differed in whether the noise took part in a similar discrimination with a panel light preceding it (N+, P→N-) or was left as a simple excitator (N+). During the test, responding to the noise and a new compound of the houselight and the noise was assessed (N, H→N). Both groups showed suppression to the noise. However, the houselight reduced suppression to the noise only in the group for which the noise was trained as the target of another discrimination. Note that, had the houselight acquired conditioned inhibitory properties during the discriminative training, it should affect responding to the noise in both groups (e.g., Rescorla, 1969). This differential transfer between negative occasion setters and conditioned inhibitors has been replicated with different stimuli and paradigms (see Holland, 1989b for review) and will be considered in the present experimental series. Theoretical issues surrounding selective transfer will be addressed in the General Discussion.

Despite its relevance for validating a model of renewal, the transfer property of contexts has not been directly addressed. If contexts act as negative occasion setters for the CSs trained in their presence, they should also modulate responding to other stimuli provided that they have been extinguished in a different context. For instance, if a cue (Y) is trained in an ABC renewal design (i.e., has been occasion set in B), and the test context (C) has had prior extinction within it with a different cue (i.e., has been trained as a negative occasion setter), then C should modulate responding to Y in an ABC renewal test. Simply put, renewal to an extinguished stimulus should be attenuated in a context where another stimulus has been extinguished.

Trask et al. (2017) discuss that contexts do transfer positive occasion-setting across targets, and draw on Swartzentruber and Bouton (1988) as evidence. Using a conditioned suppression task with rats, these authors alternated tone-US pairings in context A with tone-alone presentations in context B. Similarly, a light was reinforced in C, but not reinforced in D. This training should have endowed context A with positive occasion-setting properties for the tone (as with C for the light). In that case, context A should suppress responding, not only to the tone, but also to the light, a CS that was occasion set in a different discrimination. The results confirmed that prediction.

Trask et al. (2017) presented this work as evidence that the context shows transfer properties. However, it is possible that the recovery of the CR to the light in A was due to the stimulus simply being tested out of its extinction context, thus demonstrating renewal. Moreover, to the extent that this result represents transfer of positive occasion-setting, it does not force the conclusion that simple extinction endows contexts with *negative* occasion-setting properties. Furthermore, the procedure involved an explicit discrimination between contexts rather than simple conditioning and extinction.

A study by Swartzentruber (1993) with pigeon autoshaping addressed the possibility that contexts show the transfer properties of *negative* occasion setters. A cue (X) was conditioned in context A and extinguished in context B. A different cue (Z) was similarly conditioned in C and extinguished in D. Then, responding to X and Z was assessed in all four contexts. Renewal was observed when the stimuli were tested in their conditioning contexts (i.e., ABA renewal) and also in the context where the other stimulus was conditioned (i.e., ABC renewal). As expected, when tested in their respective extinction contexts the animals showed extinction performance. But, of most interest, renewal did not occur when the stimuli were tested in the context where the *other* stimulus had been extinguished, although that test would conceptually be an ABC test for renewal. Therefore, it appeared as though transfer of negative occasion-setting was observed. Our only criticism with this otherwise well-designed experiment is that the same result would be expected if the extinction contexts acquired conditioned inhibition during extinction (e.g., Cunningham, 1979; Glautier et al., 2013; Polack et al., 2012). That is, the contexts might have suppressed responding to any CS, rather than only ones that had undergone extinction. An occasion-setting account, instead, would require the latter.

More recently, Todd (2013, Experiment 4) conducted an experiment in instrumental conditioning to determine whether an extinction context shows occasion-setting transfer in a renewal design. The design, relabeled for consistency with our descriptions thus far, is shown in Table 1. He trained rats to perform a response (R1) in context A, and a different response (R2) in context B for the same food outcome. Then, half of the animals (the Ext-A group) had extinction of each response in the alternate context. The other half (Ext-C group) had extinction of R1 in context B, but no extinction occurred in A. Instead, R2 was extinguished in a different context (C). Thus, both groups had extinction of R1 in B, but context A could have been established as a negative occasion setter only in the Ext-A group, and C as a negative occasion setter only in the Ext-C group. Then, all animals received two tests. First, both groups were involved in ABA renewal tests. R1 responding was tested in its extinction context (B) and also in context A. Had the extinction of R2 rendered A with negative-occasion-setting properties in the Ext-A group, transfer to R1 should occur and renewal should be reduced in that group. Contrary to that expectation, both groups showed equivalent renewal.

The results of this test contradict an occasion-setting account of renewal. However, such conclusion is weakened by another variable that arises from the complexity of occasion-setting. Because

Table 1
Experimental Design of Todd (2013, Experiment 4)

Group	Acquisition	Extinction	Test 1	Test 2
Ext-A	A: R1+ B: R2+ C: . . .	A: R2- B: R1- C: . . .	B: R1-; A: R1-	B: R1-; C: R1-
Ext-C	A: R1+ B: R2+ C: . . .	A: . . . B: R1- C: R2-	B: R1-; A: R1-	B: R1-; C: R1-

Note. A, B, and C represent different contexts; R1 and R2 are different responses that may be reinforced (+) or not (-). . . . = context exposure.

the test took place in a context where both conditioning and extinction occurred, context A could have acquired positive occasion-setting properties with respect to R1 and negative occasion-setting properties relative to R2. That is, the test context could be an “ambiguous” occasion setter (Holland, 1991; Holland & Reeve, 1991; Nakajima, 1998). Even if context A was not specifically trained as a positive occasion setter in the first phase, it may have acquired such properties after extinction. Indeed, there is evidence that extinction can retrospectively alter the properties of the conditioning context (Harris, Jones, Bailey, & Westbrook, 2000).

This criticism, however, does not apply to the second test. In that case, responding to R1 was assessed again in the extinction context (B) but the other test trial was done in C, comprising an ABC renewal test. Context C was neutral in the Ext-A group, whereas the Ext-C group has had extinction of R2 within it. Importantly, because neither response had been reinforced in C, the results cannot be obscured by the possibility that C is an ambiguous occasion setter. But, again, similar renewal was found in both groups. It must be noted, however, that the size of renewal on Test 2 was considerably smaller than on Test 1, which could restrict the range in which to observe transfer.

Todd’s (2013) results are inconsistent with the idea that the extinction context acts as a negative occasion setter. However, he used an operant conditioning paradigm, and there is evidence (reviewed in Trask et al., 2017) that suggests that, in instrumental procedures, the context is likely to act as a conditioned inhibitor of the response itself. In that case, inhibition of R2 would not be expected to affect R1.

The idea that the context could be an ambiguous occasion setter prevents us from drawing firm conclusions regarding experiments that control the conditioning and extinction histories of the contexts (e.g., Bouton & Ricker, 1994; Delamater, Campese, & Westbrook, 2009; Grahame et al., 1990; Lovibond, Preston, & Mackintosh, 1984; Rescorla, 2008). With the exception of Lovibond et al. (1984) and Grahame et al. (1990), recovery has been observed in all experiments employing balanced designs where different CSs are conditioned in each context (A & B) and then extinguished in the alternate context before being tested back in their conditioning contexts. Additionally, these experiments did not include conditions where the contexts *could not* acquire occasion-setting properties against which to truly assess transfer (see also Campese & Delamater, 2013).

To summarize, there is no compelling evidence in the literature that contexts have the transfer characteristics of occasion setters, particularly negative occasion setters. In this latter case, transfer has either not been found (Todd, 2013), experiments lack control groups where transfer is not expected (Bouton & Ricker, 1994; Campese & Delamater, 2013; Delamater et al., 2009; Grahame et al., 1990; Lovibond et al., 1984; Rescorla, 2008), or do not rule out alternative explanations such as conditioned inhibition (Swartzentruber, 1993).

The objective of the experiments presented here was to assess whether extinction contexts can demonstrate transfer. We began with a predictive-learning task where there is evidence of renewal (Bustamante, Uengoer, & Lachnit, 2016; Paredes-Olay & Rosas, 1999; Üngör & Lachnit, 2006, 2008). In Experiment 1 participants had to rate the probability of some foods producing gastric malaise in different fictitious restaurants that served as contexts. Two main

cues were used. The test cue (Y) was conditioned in context A, extinguished in context B, and tested in C. Between groups, a different cue (X) was extinguished, or not, in the test context (C) to potentially endow it with negative occasion-setting properties. If there is transfer of occasion-setting, less renewal with Y should be observed when extinction of X has occurred in the test context. Note that, apart from manipulations designed to reduce the probability of the contexts becoming inhibitory (discussed below), we made no effort in Experiment 1 to determine the nature of any potential transfer (either occasion-setting or conditioned inhibition).

To fully assess an occasion-setting account, and rule out a conditioned inhibition explanation, the experimental design must manipulate the status of both the test context and the test target. The target should be one that has been either extinguished or not. Occasion-setting transfer should only appear in the former case, while a conditioned inhibitor should operate on both. Therefore, a full 2 (target occasion set by extinction, or not) × 2 (test context being an occasion setter by way of extinction, or not) is required. Experiments 2–4 followed that design. Instead of using the predictive learning task, Experiment 4 used a behavioral task.

In the experimental procedures used here, we adopted the conceptualization of context from Bouton, Nelson, and Rosas (1999) as the set of visual cues that are present during both learning and testing which are incidental to the task. That is, the procedure does not require a response directed toward them, but to the other stimuli involved in the task.

Experiment 1

The design of Experiment 1 (Exp. 1) is shown in Table 2. The task was based on the one used by Rosas and his colleagues (e.g., Aristizabal, Ramos-Álvarez, Callejas-Aguilera, & Rosas, 2016; León, Abad, & Rosas, 2011; Rosas & Callejas-Aguilera, 2006). We had special interest in mirroring both the task and the procedure used in Rosas and Callejas-Aguilera (2006), as their findings have been used to develop theories with important implications for contextual control and other related phenomena (Rosas & Callejas-Aguilera, 2006; see also Gawronski, Rydell, Vervliet, & De Houwer, 2010).

Table 2
Design of Experiment 1

Group	Acquisition	Extinction	Test
OS(C)		B: 10Y – 6F2+ C: 10X – 6F2+	C: Y
NO-OS(C)	A: 10X + 10Y + 6F1–	B: 10Y – 6F2+ C: 10F3– 6F2+	
OS(B)		B: 10Y – 6F2+ C: 10X – 6F2+	B: Y
NO-OS(B)		B: 10Y – 6F2+ C: 10F3– 6F2+	

Note. A, B, and C are different restaurants that served as contexts; X, Y, F1, F2, and F3 are different food cues that may be paired with illness (+) or not (–). Numbers refer to the number of trials with each cue. The most important cues are highlighted with bold text. OS = occasion-setting condition; NO-OS = no occasion-setting condition; (C) = test in context C; (B) = test in context B.

Two groups (OS[C] and NO-OS[C]) received an ABC renewal procedure with cue Y. The groups differed in whether the test context (C) had prior extinction of a different cue (X) within it (Occasion-Setting condition [OS]), or a never reinforced filler cue (F3) was presented instead (No Occasion-Setting condition [NO-OS]). Groups OS(B) and NO-OS(B) provided a baseline upon which to assess renewal. They had the same treatment but were tested in the extinction context (B). Pretest trials were included before the acquisition and extinction phases, to mirror the procedure of Rosas and Callejas-Aguilera (2006).

ABC renewal was expected in the NO-OS(C) group compared with its control, the NO-OS(B) group. The test for transfer comes from the OS groups. If C acquired the properties of a negative occasion setter in the OS(C) group, it should transfer its modulatory power to Y and renewal should be smaller.

Note that, during extinction, context C could acquire conditioned inhibitory properties, as opposed to occasion-setting. In either case, renewal should be less in the OS(C) group. Irrelevant cues (preceded by “F” in the table) were used to provide both reinforced and nonreinforced filler trials within each context. Although a filler cue was reinforced in C during extinction, that cue was never nonreinforced, thus C should not have any positive or ambiguous occasion-setting properties. Being interested in negative occasion-setting, we included these reinforced trials to minimize the possibilities of C acquiring inhibition. That possibility was not directly assessed until Experiment 2.

Method

Participants. Participants were college-aged volunteers recruited through announcements in the university campus. They were compensated with five euros for their collaboration.

For proper counterbalancing (CS Identity [2] × Context Identity [2] × Context Training Order [2]), we planned for three participants within each of the eight combinations (24 participants per main Group $N = 96$), giving the experiment a power of .92 to detect a large effect, according to Cohen’s rules of thumb ($\eta^2 = .14, .06, .01$, for large, medium, and small effects, respectively) and a power of .77 for an effect between medium and large (.10). Because renewal is a robust effect (e.g., Paredes-Olay & Rosas, 1999, produce an effect size of $\eta^2 = 0.497$), we had a large range to detect an effect of transfer. No volunteer who showed up was rejected, resulting in 113 participants taking part in the experiment.

Participants provided written consent and all procedures were approved by the Commission of Ethics for Research and Teaching of the University of the Basque Country UPV/EHU (M10/2015/210).

Apparatus. The task was run on five Dell OptiPlex computers with 22-in. monitors with an aspect ratio of 1.6 (width/height). The resolution was set at 1,280 × 800 pixels. A trapezoidal box constructed of black foam board with rectangular ends and the front face uncovered was placed over the monitor and keyboard. The opening was 70 by 70 cm and the back wall was 70 by 50 cm (width × height), the overall length of the side walls was 1 m. The front opening allowed participants to sit at the table with their head and shoulders just inside the box, isolating each participant. The procedure was implemented using the E-prime 2.0 Professional software (Psychology Software Tools, Pittsburgh, PA), and the

participants interacted with the computer using the mouse. Stimuli and instructions were presented in Spanish.

Food names were chosen from the pool selected by García-Gutiérrez and Rosas (2003). Tuna was used as cue Y. Garlic and Corn were counterbalanced as cues X and F3. Two additional cues were used as fillers, F1 (Eggs) and F2 (Cucumbers). Three fictitious restaurants served as contexts A, B and C. Context A was a restaurant called The Danish Pantry, the other two restaurants (The Canadian Cabin and The Swiss Cow) were counterbalanced as B and C.

Each trial consisted of a *customer screen*, a *stimulus screen*, and a *feedback screen* (see Figure 2). The *customer screen* (top panel of Figure 2) had the sentence “Loading the file of (a randomly chosen name and surname)” on the middle. Below, another sentence read “Click to continue.”

On the top of the *stimulus screen* (middle panel of Figure 2) a sentence read “This person ate at the restaurant (name of the restaurant).” On the middle it was written “This person ate (name of the food).” Below, a sentence read “Click with the mouse on the scale to indicate the probability that this person presents diarrhea.” In the bottom of the screen, there was a 0–100 scale containing 21 green buttons. Each of them had a number representing a 5-point interval on the scale. To facilitate interpretation of the scale, the words *none*, *little*, *quite*, and *much* were evenly separated from each other, covering the whole scale.

The *feedback screen* (bottom panel of Figure 2) contained the name of the restaurant at the middle top. Below a sentence read “This person (had diarrhea/had no disorder).” Finally, in the middle bottom it was written “Click to continue.”

Different logos were used to represent each restaurant. The name of The Danish Pantry appeared within a green square. The name The Canadian Cabin was written within a blue rectangle with rounded corners. The name of the restaurant The Swiss Cow was presented within a yellow oval. Context changes were announced on a separate screen that read “Now you should analyze the files of the people that ate at restaurant (name of the restaurant).”

The foods’ names were written in blue capital letters. The words “had diarrhea” in the *feedback screen* were presented in red. Blue was used for the alternate outcome (“had no disorder”). Black font was used in the remainder text. The screen background was white in all screen types.

Procedure. The 32 experimental conditions that resulted from the combination of the grouping variable (4), CS identity (2), Context identity (2), and Context training order (2; see below for description of these variables) were randomly assigned to participants without replacement until each condition had been assigned once. Then, the conditions were replaced into the pool. The participant read and signed the informed consent and was placed at the computer.

Four screens were used to deliver the instructions. The participant advanced these screens by pressing a green button at the lower right corner with the word “Continue.” The first screen read:

Before beginning, we want to thank you for your presence in this experiment. Without people like you, this research will not be possible. You should know that in this task there are no correct or incorrect answers. We want to study the basic mechanisms which are present in all people and we need you to participate with the highest interest possible. The data provided by you will be anonymous. If, after

Figure 2. Structure and layout of a trial in Experiments 1 and 2. Customer's screen (top), stimulus screen (middle) and feedback screen (bottom) showing the outcome of a conditioning trial. See the online article for the color version of this figure.

finishing the task, you want to know what has been tested, ask the experimenter. If you do not want to continue, you can leave the cabin now.

The second screen had the following text:

Recent developments in food technology have led to the chemical synthesis of food. This creates a great advantage as is very low cost and easy to both store and transport. This revolution in the food industry may solve hunger in third world countries.

The third screen read:

However, it has been detected that some foods produce gastric problems in some people. For this reason, we are interested in selecting a group of experts to identify the foods that lead to some type of illness, and how it appears in each case.

The fourth screen included the text:

You are about to receive a selection test where you will be looking at the files of persons that have ingested different foods in a specific restaurant. You will have to indicate the probability that the intake of such food will result in gastric problems. To respond you should click the option that you consider appropriate. Your response will be random at the beginning, but do not worry; little by little you will become an expert.

Then, the participant received a demonstration trial identical to those used during the experiment except that a different cue (Pasta) was used. This trial took place in The Danish Pantry and was not reinforced. At this point, a screen read "Very good, you have just familiarized yourself with the procedure. Press the CONTINUE button to start." Once the participant pressed such button, the experimental part began. The trials were self-paced and the length of the experiment varied by participant (15–20 min, approximate).

Pretest 1. The participants read the sentence "Before beginning, please, answer the following question." Then, they were tested with Y in their test context. The OS(C) and NO-OS(C) groups were tested in context C; the other two were tested in B. No feedback was given on pretest trials.

Acquisition. Acquisition began without announcement after pretest 1. All participants had 10 conditioning trials with X, 10 conditioning trials with Y, and six nonreinforced trials with F1 in context A. Training was organized in two blocks, each of which contained five trials with X, five with Y, and three trials with F1 randomly intermixed.

Pretest 2. Pretest 2 proceeded as pretest 1, except that it was given with no announcement.

Extinction. Extinction took place in contexts B and C. In B, all groups had 10 extinction trials with Y and six reinforced trials with F2. In C, the OS groups had 10 extinction trials with X. The NO-OS groups had 10 nonreinforced trials with F3 instead. Additionally, all participants had six conditioning trials with F2 in context C.

Extinction was organized in four blocks of eight trials each. A B-block contained five trials with Y and three with F2 in context B. A C-block had five trials with either X or F3 and three trials with F2 in C. Trials were randomly intermixed within blocks. The order in which the blocks were presented was counterbalanced: half of the participants in each group received the sequence BCCB (where letters represent the context used in each block); the other half had the sequence CBBC.

Test. The final test proceeded as pretest 2.

Data analysis. The computer recorded the predictive ratings given in each trial. These ratings were analyzed using mixed (within-between) analysis of variance (ANOVA). Effect sizes are reported as partial-eta squared (η_p^2). Ninety-five percent confidence intervals around η_p^2 were calculated using software for Excel available in Nelson (2016) and are reported in the subscripts following η_p^2 . Where a range of significant results are

reported (e.g., $F_s \geq X$, $p_s \leq Y$), the confidence intervals reflect the lower limit on the smallest significant effect and the upper limit on the largest significant effect. Where relevant for supporting a lack of effect, the probability of the null hypothesis (H0) was estimated using the techniques presented by Wagenmakers (2007).

Results

Screening. Data were removed if ratings in two of the last three conditioning trials with each cue did not achieve a value of 70. Five participants were removed from the OS(C) group, five from the NO-OS(C) condition, three were removed from the OS(B) group, and two from the NO-OS(B) group. The final group sizes were 25 for the former two groups and 24 for the later ones. Final N was 98 leaving the earlier power calculations practically unchanged.

Pretest 1. Ratings in each group were very close to each other during the first assessment of Y (range 30.76 to 38.88). The lack of differences was confirmed with an OSdesign (OS vs. NO-OS) \times TestContext (C vs. B) ANOVA that showed no significant effects, $p_s \geq .18$.

Acquisition. An OSdesign (OS vs. NO-OS) \times TestContext (C vs. B) \times Cue (X or Y) \times Trials ANOVA revealed a significant effect of Trials, $F(9, 846) = 283.08$, $p < .0001$, $\eta_p^2 = .75_{(.73-.77)}$, $MSE = 309.54$. Acquisition to Y is shown in Figure 3A. Average ratings with X (not shown) increased from 27.31 (first trial) to 96.94 (last trial). There was an unexpected, but small, OSdesign \times TestContext \times Trials interaction, $F(9, 846) = 2.45$, $p = .009$, $\eta_p^2 = .025_{(.003-.034)}$, $MSE = 309.54$. No other effects were significant, $p_s \leq .17$.

The interaction above was followed with TestContext (C vs. B) \times Trials ANOVAs within each level of OSdesign. There was a TestContext effect, $F(1, 47) = 23.23$, $p < .0001$, $\eta_p^2 = .33_{(.15-.47)}$, $MSE = 1576.45$, and a TestContext \times Trials interaction, $F(9, 423) = 2.95$, $p = .002$, $\eta_p^2 = .06_{(.01-.08)}$, $MSE = 295.11$, in the NO-OS conditions. The NO-OS(B) group gave slightly lower average ratings ($\bar{x} = 74.71$) than the NO-OS(C) condition ($\bar{x} = 86.94$) on every trial, $F(1, 47)_{\text{range}} = 4.3-14.58$, $p_{\text{range}} =$

$.044-3.92 \times 10^{-4}$, $\eta_p^2_{\text{range}} = .08-.24_{(.001-.39)}$, $MSE_{\text{range}} = 116.63-839.21$. Such a tendency was not present in the OS groups, where there were no significant effects involving TestContext, $p_s \geq .23$. At this point all groups had received the same treatment, so there is no clear explanation for these differences.

Pretest 2. Pretest 2 was assessed with an OSdesign (OS vs. NO-OS) \times TestContext (C vs. B) ANOVA. No significant effects were found, $p_s \geq .26$. Mean ratings ranged from 69.04 to 78.68 among groups.

To assess whether testing Y out of its conditioning context resulted in a loss of conditioning performance, we conducted a Phase (last Y + trial, $\bar{x} = 95.68$ vs. pretest 2, $\bar{x} = 75.05$) \times Group (all four groups) ANOVA. The effect of Phase was significant, $F(1, 94) = 37.94$, $p < .0001$, $\eta_p^2 = .29_{(.16-.396)}$, $MSE = 547.81$, with no effects involving the Group variable, $F_s(3,94) \leq 1.62$, $p_s \geq .19$, $MSE_{\text{range}} = 547.81-665.09$.

Extinction. Figure 3B shows extinction of Y. An OSdesign (OS vs. NO-OS) \times TestContext (C vs. B) \times Trials ANOVA revealed an effect of Trials, $F(9, 846) = 34.94$, $p < .0001$, $\eta_p^2 = .27_{(.22-.303)}$, $MSE = 562.42$, and an unexpected (but small) effect of TestContext, $F(1, 95) = 3.97$, $p = .049$, $\eta_p^2 = .04_{(.00007-.12)}$, $MSE = 895.82$, that resulted from slightly better extinction in the groups that were to be tested in C ($\bar{x} = 14.16, 17.97$, for Test C and Test B, respectively). No other effects were significant, $p_s \geq .15$.

Ratings to X (not shown) decreased during extinction in the OS groups. A TestContext (C vs. B) \times Trials ANOVA revealed an effect of Trials, $F(9, 423) = 17.98$, $p < .0001$, $\eta_p^2 = .28_{(.21-.32)}$, $MSE = 464.5$, and a main effect of TestContext, $F(1, 47) = 6.13$, $p = .017$, $\eta_p^2 = .12_{(.01-.26)}$, $MSE = 893.18$, that was attributable to slightly less extinction in the OS(C) group, $\bar{x} = 17.82$, than in the OS(B) group, $\bar{x} = 11.13$.

In summary, conditioning to X and Y was successful, as was extinction of Y in the relevant groups. There was a minor pre-existing trend for lower responding in the NO-OS(B) condition. There was slightly better extinction to Y in the groups to be tested in C, and X extinguished slightly poorer in the OS(C) condition than in the OS(B) condition.

Figure 3. Results of Experiment 1. (A) Mean predictive ratings to cue Y in each conditioning trial. (B) Ratings given during each trial of the extinction phase. (C) Performance in the test. (D) Performance during the test minus performance in the last extinction trial with Y. Vertical bars represent the standard error of the mean. OS = occasion-setting condition; NO = no occasion-setting condition; (C) = test in context C; (B) = test in context B.

The lower responding in the NO-OS(B) condition would make renewal appear to be inflated. To help compensate for these minor differences we included the last trial of extinction as an additional baseline against which to assess test performance.

Test. The mean predictive ratings during the test are shown in Figure 3C. The differences in the ratings between the test and the last extinction trial (the size of the renewal effect) are shown in Figure 3D. Those differences are what is represented by the effect of Renewal in the following analysis. An OSdesign (OS vs. NO-OS) \times TestContext (B or C) \times Renewal (last Y-trial vs. test) ANOVA yielded a significant Renewal, $F(1, 94) = 28.44, p < .0001, \eta_p^2 = .23_{(.12-.34)}, MSE = 752.53$, and a TestContext \times Renewal interaction, $F(1, 94) = 13.31, p < .0001, \eta_p^2 = .12_{(.04-.23)}, MSE = 752.53$. Renewal was significant in the groups tested in C, $F(1, 49) = 34.56, p < .0001, \eta_p^2 = .41_{(.23-.54)}, MSE = 896.33$, but it was not in the groups tested in B, $F(1, 47) = 1.81, p = .19, MSE = 577.7$, indicating that extinction was complete as there was no change from the last trial to the test. The lack of effects involving the OSdesign variable, $ps \geq .19$, especially the lack of a significant three-way interaction necessary to support a transfer interpretation, $F(1, 94) = .043, p = .84, \eta_p^2 = .0004_{(.000001-.02)}, MSE = 752.53, P_{H0/D} = .91$, indicates equivalent renewal between groups. The effect of OSdesign was also not significant when assessed on the test trial alone in the groups tested in C, $F(1, 48) = .34, p = .56, \eta_p^2 = .007_{(.000002-.09)}, MSE = 1799.26, P_{H0/D} = .86$.

Discussion

Exp. 1 assessed whether an extinction context shows transfer to a CS extinguished in a different context. Groups OS(C) and NO-OS(C) were tested with Y in an ABC renewal design where extinction of X had either occurred in C, or not, respectively. To assess renewal, two other groups had the same treatment but were tested in context B. Less renewal should be observed in group OS(C) if context C had acquired occasion-setting properties. A result that would be also expected if it acquired conditioned inhibition.

In conditioning, there was a tendency in the NO-OS(C) group to give higher ratings than the NO-OS(B) condition. Comparison between these groups served as the baseline for ABC renewal. Because such difference was not present in the OS groups, had that pattern persisted on test, reduced renewal in the OS groups attrib-

utable to the experimental treatment would be confounded with these preexisting differences. Despite the head-start there were no differences on test.

During extinction of Y, the groups that were to be tested in C showed slightly lower responding. If such tendency persisted on the test, the magnitude of renewal would appear to be reduced. However, such reduction was present both groups (there was no interaction with the OSdesign variable), leaving the comparisons between them relatively unaffected.

No transfer was found at test. Similar recovery was observed regardless of whether extinction had occurred in the test context. This conclusion is further supported by the fact that there were minor preexisting differences in a direction that would look like greater renewal in the control (NO-OS) groups.

Conclusions are slightly obscured since sampling error resulted in slightly weaker extinction of X in the OS(C) group, where occasion-setting transfer could be observed. Thus, C may not have been so well established as a negative occasion setter in that group, reducing the possibilities of finding transfer. Experiment 2 replicated the same basic design while including groups to differentiate between the occasion-setting and conditioned-inhibition accounts, should transfer occur.

Experiment 2

Experiment 2 (Exp. 2) had the same objective as Exp. 1, to determine whether extinction of a CS in the test context can reduce ABC renewal. The procedure was modified to simplify the task and, maybe, increase the range in which we might observe transfer by producing greater renewal. Additionally, Exp. 2 was designed to identify the source for any transfer that might occur.

The design (shown in Table 3) was made simpler by separating the training of the two targets and contexts into different phases, thus reducing the number of within-phase context changes. The first four groups in the table form a 2×2 factorial design manipulating whether or not extinction occurred in the test context (OC vs. NC distinction) and whether or not the test stimulus Y was extinguished (OT vs. NT distinction). In phase 1, X was conditioned in context D in all groups. In phase 2, X was extinguished in C (OC groups), or not (NC groups). This treatment should endow context C with either negative-occasion-setting or conditioned inhibitory properties in the OC groups. In phase 3, all

Table 3
Design of Experiments 2 and 3

Group	Phase 1	Phase 2	Phase 3	Phase 4	Test
OC-OT		C: 10X - 3F3+		B: 10Y - 3F3+	
NC-OT	D: 10X + 3F3+	C: 10F1 - 3F3+	A: 10Y + 3F3+	B: 10Y - 3F3+	C: Y
OC-NT		C: 10X - 3F3+		B: 10F2 - 3F3+	
NC-NT		C: 10F1 - 3F3+		B: 10F2 - 3F3+	
OC-OT (B)	D: 10X + 3F3+	C: 10X - 3F3+	A: 10Y + 3F3+	B: 10Y - 3F3+	B: Y
NC-OT (B)		C: 10F1 - 3F3+		B: 10Y - 3F3+	

Note. A, B, C, and D are different restaurants that served as contexts; X, Y, F1, F2, and F3 are different food cues that may be followed by illness (+) or not (-). Numbers refer to the number of trials with each cue. The most important cues are highlighted with bold text. OT = occasion-setting target; NT = no occasion-setting target; OC = occasion-setting context; NC = no occasion-setting context. Experiment 2 contained all six groups in the table. Experiment 3 used the first four groups presented here (context first groups) and other four (target first groups) that had the treatments in phase 3 and 4 occurring before that received in phases 1 and 2.

groups were conditioned with Y in context A. Then, in phase 4, Y was extinguished in B (OT groups), or not (NT groups). This should have made Y an appropriate target for an occasion setter in the OT groups. Finally, Y was tested in C.

In the NC-OT group, an extinguished cue was tested in a neutral context, so ABC renewal was expected. In the OC-OT group renewal should be reduced if extinction of X endowed C with either occasion-setting or conditioned-inhibition properties. In the NC-NT group, a nonextinguished cue was tested in a neutral context, so transfer of conditioning was expected. In the OC-NT group, a nonextinguished cue was tested in a context where extinction of X occurred. Had that treatment endowed C with inhibitory properties, ratings to Y should be reduced. To the contrary, no reduction is expected in this group if C acquired occasion-setting properties, since a nonextinguished cue has been shown to be an unsuitable target for transfer.

Two groups (those at the bottom of Table 3) were tested within their extinction context (B). The OC-OT(B) group had extinction of X in C and thus served as baseline for renewal for the OC-OT condition; the group NC-OT(B) was used to assess renewal in the NC-OT condition.

In Exp. 1 we used labels to represent both the food cues and the restaurant contexts, requiring participants to interpret these labels and infer that the cues were presented within the contexts. To try to enhance the roles played by the stimuli, in this experiment the cues were pictures of actual foods that were presented on a larger background image of actual restaurants. The method and stimuli were adapted from Ogallar et al. (2019). Pretest trials were eliminated in this and the following experiments.

Method

Participants. Counterbalancing (CS Identity [6] × Context Identity [2]), required a minimum of 12 participants per group (six groups), so initially 72 participants were recruited. After screening the data, 13 more people were needed to maintain adequate group sizes, leading to a total of 85 college-aged volunteers taking part in this study. The experiment had a power of .72 to detect a large effect, and .52 to detect an intermediate-large effect ($\eta^2 = .1$). Details not specified here or in the following sections of the Method were the same as those of Exp. 1.

Apparatus. The task was run using SuperLab Pro (Cedrus Corporation) software. The stimuli were modified with respect to Exp. 1 (see Figure 4). On the middle of the *customers screen*, the sentence “next customer” was presented at the beginning of each trial. The *stimulus screen* (top panel of Figure 4) contained a picture of a real restaurant that occupied approximately 65% of the central part of the screen. The name of the restaurant appeared in black bold font within a white square on the picture’s top left corner. A square in the middle of the restaurant’s picture contained the picture of the food. Above the restaurant’s picture, a sentence read “How much diarrhea will this person suffer from?.” Below that, there was a 0–100 scale similar to that used in Exp. 1, except that, a “poop” symbol derived from the popular (circa 2020) Internet emoticon “Pile of Poo” was presented above the words “Little” “Quite” and “Much,” with its size increasing accordingly.

The *feedback screen* (bottom panel of Figure 4) was like the *stimulus screen* except that the question was eliminated, the scale was replaced by a red rectangle containing the sentence

“Response Recorded,” and the outcome was presented in a white rectangle just below the food’s picture. The outcome could be either “Much diarrhea” (in capital red font) or “No diarrhea” (in capital black font).

The images used for representing the restaurants were considerably different from each other. The restaurant named The Oven was a country-style restaurant with wood furniture and a wood-fired oven in the back wall. The walls were ocher with stone details. The Modern Restaurant had smooth black walls that contrasted with colorful-metal chairs. Small tables were individually illuminated with lamps made of green glass bottles. The picture of The Blue Lake restaurant showed a terrace placed next to a lake surrounded by mountains. A white awning covered the tables and wicker chairs. Finally, the image of The Alley restaurant (see Figure 4) showed tables in a shadowy alley on a sunny day. Context changes were announced as in the previous experiment with the correspondent image.

Cucumbers and Corn were used as cues X and F3, respectively. The identity of Y, F1 and F2 was fully counterbalanced as Fish, Garlic or Eggs. Within each group, participants were assigned to one of the six possible combinations of these cues. The Modern Restaurant and The Oven served as contexts A and D, respectively. The Blue Lake and The Alley were counterbalanced as B and C.

Procedure. Instructions were provided orally. Once seated at the computer desk, the participant was presented with a demonstration trial. The experimenter informed the participants that they had to predict the amount of diarrhea a fictitious customer will experience from the information available on the screen. The food (Chicken) and restaurant (The Lilies) used in this trial were not used again. Once the participant made his or her prediction on the scale, a feedback screen with the two possible outcomes (Much diarrhea and No diarrhea) was presented. The participant was informed that only one of the outcomes would appear in the following trials. Then, he or she was told to click in any part of the screen to begin the experiment and was left alone. After clicking, the first instruction screen in the previous experiment (“Before beginning . . .”) was presented and the experiment began.

Phase 1. All participants received 10 reinforced trials with X and three reinforced trials with F3 in context D. One F3 trial divided the X trials in two blocks of five trials. The other F3 trials were given at the very beginning and at the end of the phase (one in each position).

Phase 2. Phase 2 took place in context C. The OC groups received 10 extinction trials with X. The NC groups had 10 nonreinforced trials with F1 instead. All received three additional conditioning trials with F3 distributed as in phase 1.

Phase 3. In phase 3 all groups received 10 conditioning trials with Y in context A and three reinforced F3 trials distributed as in prior phases.

Phase 4. Phase 4 was carried out in context B. Half of the OC participants had 10 extinction trials with Y (OC-OT group). The other half (OC-NT group) received 10 nonreinforced trials with F2. The NC group was also split by halves depending on whether the participants had 10 extinction trials with Y (NC-OT group), or 10 nonreinforced trials with F2 (NC-NT group). Three reinforced F3 trials were given as in prior phases.

Test. All groups mentioned thus far were tested with Y in context C. Two additional groups, the OC-OT(B) and NC-OT(B)

¿Qué cantidad de diarrea padecerá esta persona?

Figure 4. Structure and layout of a trial in Experiment 2. *Stimulus screen* (top) and *feedback screen* (bottom) showing the outcome of an extinction trial. See the online article for the color version of this figure.

groups, had the same treatment as the OC-OT and NC-OT groups, respectively, but were tested in B.

Data analysis. Data were analyzed as in Exp. 1.

Results

Screening. Participant's data were screened as in Exp. 1. Five participants were removed from group NC-OT, three from group OC-NT, two from group NC-NT, and three from group NC-

OT(B). Those people were replaced to ensure adequate representation in the conditions and maintain equal group sizes ($n = 12$). Removal was independent of Group, $X^2(5) = 7.47, p = .19$.

Conditioning and extinction with X. Conditioning with X was assessed with a Group (all 6 groups) \times Trials ANOVA. An effect of Trials, $F(9, 594) = 98.48, p < .0001, \eta_p^2 = .599_{(.555-.626)}$, $MSE = 272.24$, reflected the increase in the mean predictive ratings, from 33.82 on the first trial, to 95 on the last. There were no effects involving the Group variable, $ps \geq .37$.

The analyses of the OC groups during extinction of X revealed an effect of Trials, $F(9, 297) = 95.99, p < .0001, \eta^2_p = .74_{(.698-.767)}, MSE = 298.54$. The lack of effects involving Group variable, $ps \geq .88$, indicated similar extinction in all the OC groups. Ratings averaged 0.76 by the end of extinction.

Conditioning and extinction with Y. Performance in phase 3 is shown in Figure 5A. The increase in the ratings to Y was confirmed by a Group (all six groups) \times Trials ANOVA that revealed an effect of Trials, $F(9, 594) = 124.6, p < .0001, \eta^2_p = .65_{(.61-.68)}, MSE = 178.28$. No significant effects involved the Group variable, $ps \geq .56$.

Figure 5B shows the mean ratings in the groups that had extinction of Y in phase 4. Extinction was confirmed by a Group (the 4 OT groups) \times Trials ANOVA that revealed an effect of Trials, $F(9, 396) = 177.17, p < .0001, \eta^2_p = .80_{(.77-.82)}, MSE = 202.66$. Y was similarly extinguished between groups, as indicated by the lack of significant effects involving the Group variable, $ps \geq .77$.

Test. Performance at test is shown in Figure 5C. As in Exp. 1 we further assessed renewal by comparing the last training trial and the test (differences shown in Figure 5D). An analysis of the differences is represented by the Renewal factor in the analysis below. A Renewal (last Y-trial vs. test) \times OSctxt (OC-OT group vs. NC-OT group, open symbols in the figure) ANOVA yielded a significant effect of Renewal, $F(1, 22) = 61.61, p < .0001, \eta^2_p = .74_{(.53-.81)}, MSE = 892.95$, confirming a robust recovery of the

response in these groups. The lack of effects involving the OSctxt variable, $F_s \leq 1$, especially the lack of an interaction $F(1, 22) = .41, p = .53, \eta^2_p = .02_{(.000004-.1)}, MSE = 892.95, P_{H0/D} = .8$, indicates similar renewal in both groups. The effect of OSctxt was absent also when considering only the test trial, $F(1, 22) = .42, p = .52, \eta^2_p = .02_{(.000004-.2)}, MSE = 1810.51, P_{H0/D} = .8$.

A TestContext (test in C, open symbols in Figure 5 vs. in B, gray symbols) \times OSctxt (OC-OT groups vs. NC-OT groups) ANOVA was run on the test trial to assess the level of renewal in the groups tested in C, and to see whether any effect of extinction of X

between groups could be detected. There was a main effect of TestContext, $F(1, 44) = 44.08, p < .0001, \eta^2_p = .5_{(.31-.62)}, MSE = 1113.59$, but no effect of the OSctxt variable, $F < 1$, nor an interaction with it, $F(1, 44) = 1.03, p = .32, \eta^2_p = .02_{(.000002-.1)}, MSE = 1113.59, P_{H0/D} = .8$. Renewal was equal regardless of the treatment of the test context.

To assess the effect of extinction of X in the test context on a nonextinguished cue (i.e., condition inhibition) an OSctxt (OC-NT vs. NC-NT, black symbols in Figure 5) \times Trials (last Y + trial vs. Test) ANOVA was conducted. None of the variables were significant, $ps \geq .24$. The lack of an interaction, $F(1, 22) = .027, p = .87, \eta^2_p = .001_{(.000006-.08)}, MSE = 78.6, P_{H0/D} = .9$, indicates that

C did not acquire the properties of a conditioned inhibitor. The effect of OSctxt was also absent when assessed on the test trial alone, $F(1, 22) = .86, p = .36, \eta^2_p = .04_{(.000004-.22)}, MSE = 120.83, P_{H0/D} = .76$.

Discussion

Exp. 2 was designed to determine whether there is transfer of extinction across extinction contexts and identify the mechanism underlying such transfer. All participants had conditioning of a cue in context A, extinction in B, and a test in C. Whether the test context had extinction of another cue within it (OC groups) or not (NC groups) was factorially combined with whether the test cue was established as a potential occasion-setting target by way of extinction (OT groups) or not (NT groups). According to one of the apparent properties of occasion setters, transfer should occur best when both conditions are met (e.g., Holland, 1989b; Lamarre & Holland, 1987). If that were the case, the renewal effect observed in the NC-OT group should be reduced in the OC-OT group. Such a reduction would also be expected if the context had acted as a conditioned inhibitor. However, no differential renewal was observed. The results with respect to a lack of conditioned inhibition are further supported by equivalent responding to a

Figure 5. Results of Experiment 2. (A) Mean predictive ratings to cue Y on each conditioning trial. (B) Responding during each of the extinction trials. (C) Ratings given on the test trial. (D) Performance during the test minus performance in the last training trial with Y. Vertical bars represent the standard error of the mean. OT = occasion-setting target; NT = no occasion-setting target; OC = occasion-setting context; NC = no occasion-setting context.

nonextinguished cue regardless of the test context treatment in the NT groups.

Experiment 3

Neither of the previous experiments showed evidence of transfer of occasion-setting or conditioned inhibition accrued to the extinction context. Given the relevance of these results in their failure to support a widely accepted account of renewal (Bouton, 1993, 2004), and the fact that those were all null results, Experiment 3 (Exp. 3) replicated Exp. 2 but introduced some procedural modifications to further strengthen the conclusions obtained thus far.

This experiment differed in three aspects from Exp. 2. First, we counterbalanced the order in which the test context and target were trained. In Exp. 2 the test context was trained as a potential occasion setter in phases 1 and 2 while the target was trained as an occasion-setting target in phases 3 and 4 (see the former groups in Table 3). Exp. 3 preserved those groups but added another four groups where the target manipulation occurred first (see description of Table 3). Second, as Exp. 2 showed that extinction was complete at the end of training, the two groups tested in context B were not included in the present design.

A final difference with Exp. 2 was the question used in the *stimulus screen*. Exp. 2 asked for the *amount* of diarrhea the customer will experience. There are two potential issues to note. First, the question assumes that the outcome will be present; and, second, the possible outcomes on the *feedback screen* (Much diarrhea/No diarrhea) were the most extreme options in the rating scale. That poses the possibility that the participants' answers, though affected by the strength of their expectations, may not adequately reflect the graded strength of that expectation. In this experiment, we returned to the question used in Exp.1 and asked for the *probability* of the customer of having diarrhea, with the outcomes being no diarrhea, or much diarrhea.

Method

Participants. For proper counterbalancing (CS Identity [6] × Context Identity [2]), we planned for 12 participants in each of the eight groups used in this experiment ($N = 96$). However, because no volunteer who showed up was rejected, eventually 188 participants took part in this study ($n = 47$). The experiment had a power of .998 to detect a large effect, and a power of .98 to detect an intermediate-large effect. Participants were recruited and compensated as in prior experiments.

Apparatus. The only difference from Exp 2. concerned the *stimulus screen*, where the question "How much diarrhea will this person experience?" was replaced by the sentence "What is the probability that this person will have Diarrhea?"

Procedure. For the groups that had the context manipulation before the target manipulation, the procedure was the same as in Exp. 2. The groups that had the target manipulation first, experienced the same phases but in the order phase 3, phase 4, phase 1 and phase 2 relative to Exp. 2. All groups were tested with the test cue (Y) out of its extinction context, in C.

Data analysis. Predictive ratings were analyzed as in the previous experiments.

Results

Screening. Screening was done as in prior experiments. Among the participants that had the context manipulation first, one participant was removed from the OC-OT group and another from the NC-OT group. Among those that had the target manipulation first, one participant was removed from the OC-OT group, and two from the OC-NT and NC-NT groups. Those participants were replaced to equate group sizes ($ns = 24$). Removal was independent of Group, $X^2(7) = 5.35, p = .62$.

A problem with our programming resulted in the loss of the ratings by four participants on the first conditioning trial with X. Though experienced the same events, the data were not recorded. To avoid eliminating those subjects in the analysis of conditioning with X, they were assigned the group mean of the first X+ trial. The degrees of freedom for error were reduced accordingly on analyses involving these replaced data.

Conditioning with X. During training, there were no effects of the Order variable that cannot be generally accounted for by learning-to-learn effects, where conditioning and extinction with one cue facilitates the same treatments with another cue (Balea, Sanjuan, & Nelson, 2018). Therefore, this variable was omitted to simplify the presentation of the more important effects.

Conditioning of X (not shown) was assessed with an OSctxt (OC vs. NC) × OStarget (OT vs. NT) × Trials ANOVA.

The analyses yielded an effect of Trials, $F(9, 1654) = 453.32, p <$

$.0001, \eta_p^2 = .711_{(.693-.713)}, MSE = 179.46$. Mean responding increased from 29.71 on the first training trial to 96.42 on the last. No other significant effects were found, $F_s \leq 1.24, ps \geq .266, MSE_{range} = 179.46-1515.13$.

Conditioning with Y. Conditioning with Y is shown in Figure 6A. An OSctxt (OC vs. NC) × OStarget (OT vs. NT) × Trials ANOVA showed a significant effect of Trials, $F(9, 1656) = 261.56, p < .0001, \eta_p^2 = .587_{(.562-.606)}, MSE = 189.64$. As the figure suggests, the lack of other effects, $F_s \leq 1.26, ps \geq .252, MSE_{range} = 189.64-693.71$, confirmed the lack of preexisting differences between groups.

Extinction of X. Extinction of X, assessed in the OC groups with an OStarget (OT vs. NT) × Trials ANOVA, yielded a Trials effect, $F(9, 810) = 224.82, p < .0001, \eta_p^2 = .714_{(.687-.732)}, MSE = 302.04$. No other effects were significant, $F_s \leq 1.75, ps \geq .075, MSE_{range} = 302.04-1484.22$.

Extinction of Y. Extinction of Y (Figure 6B) was assessed in the OT groups with an OSctxt (OC vs. NC) × Trials ANOVA. The analyses showed Trials and OSctxt effects that were superseded by their interaction, $F(9, 846) = 2.18, p < .021, \eta_p^2 = .023_{(.002-.031)}, MSE = 330.86$. The interaction arose from a difference on Trial 2,

$F(1, 94) = 5.7, p < .019, \eta_p^2 = .057_{(.005-.146)}, MSE = 908.53$, where the NC-OT groups responded more ($\bar{x} = 20.31$) than the OC-OT groups ($\bar{x} = 5.63$).

Test. Figure 6C shows performance at test. Figure 6D shows performance at test minus performance on the last training trial. In the OT groups, this difference represents the size of the renewal effect. To assess the transfer of either extinction (in the OT groups) or conditioning (in the NT groups), we ran a Context Change (last trial with Y vs. test) × Order (Context manipulation first vs. Target manipulation first) × OSctxt (OC vs. NC) × OStarget (OT vs. NT) ANOVA. The Order variable was included to determine whether it had any impact on the findings observed in Exp. 2. The

Figure 6. Results of Experiment 3. (A) Mean predictive ratings on each conditioning trial with Y. (B) Ratings during extinction of Y in the OT groups. (C) Mean ratings during the test. (D) Performance during the test minus performance in the last training trial with Y. Vertical bars represent the standard error of the mean. See text for details. OT = occasion-setting target; NT = no occasion-setting target; OC = occasion-setting context; NC = no occasion-setting context.

analyses yielded only Context Change and OStarget effects that were superseded by their interaction, $F(1, 184) = 206.34$, $p < .0001$, $\eta_p^2 = .53_{(.45-.59)}$, $MSE = 544.79$. No significant effects involving the Order variable were found ($ps \geq .214$).

Simple effects showed an effect of Context Change both when the target was not extinguished (NT groups), $F(1, 95) = 4.6$, $p = .035$, $\eta_p^2 = .046_{(.002-.13)}$, $MSE = 82.58$, and when it was (OT groups), $F(1, 95) = 205.79$, $p < .0001$, $\eta_p^2 = .68_{(.595-.74)}$, $MSE = 1004.54$. The effect in the NT groups indicates a generalization decrement between the last conditioning trial ($\bar{x} = 96.88$) and the test ($\bar{x} = 94.06$). The effect in the OT groups indicates a recovery of the ratings when the context changes between the last extinction trial ($\bar{x} = 0.63$) and the test ($\bar{x} = 66.26$).

A conditioned inhibition account would mean a Context Change \times OSctxt interaction, but that interaction was not reliable, $F(1, 184) = 1.96$, $p = .16$, $\eta_p^2 = .011_{(.0000005-.048)}$, $MSE = 544.79$, $P_{HO/D} = .83$. An occasion-setting account would be a Context Change \times OSctxt \times OStarget interaction. Again, that interaction was not reliable, $F(1, 184) = .069$, $p = .79$, $\eta_p^2 = .0004$, $MSE = 544.79$, $P_{HO/D} = .93$.

Discussion

The design and logic of this experiment paralleled that of Exp. 2. The order of the phases of putative occasion-setting training for the contexts and target cues was counterbalanced. The results were the same as those of Exp. 2. Renewal was robust in the groups tested in the ABC renewal design regardless of whether the test context had extinction within it or not. That is, transfer of potential negative occasion-setting was not observed. Neither do the results support the idea that extinction endowed the context with conditioned inhibitory properties. Testing an excitator out of its conditioning context provoked a small decrement in the response, but the decrement was similar regardless of whether the cue was tested in a context where extinction took place or not. That a decrement occurred in the context where extinction had not taken place

suggests that the data are not so far into a response ceiling that an effect of context inhibition could not be detected.

Experiment 4

Experiment 4 (Exp. 4) addressed the same question with a behavioral method that has been used to demonstrate renewal in the absence of direct context-outcome associations (Nelson et al., 2011). In this procedure, participants acquire a high rate of mouse clicking in a video game by linking that behavior to firing torpedoes at a spaceship for points. At times, the spaceship attacks and drains the participants' power, leaving them unable to move for several seconds. Those attacks are signaled by sensor lights, and the power drain can be avoided if participants suppress their torpedo firing during the sensor. Contexts are provided by different background galaxies.

The logic of the design (shown in Table 4) was the same as in Exp. 2 and 3. In the first phase a red sensor (R) predicted the attack

Table 4
Design of Experiment 4

Group	Conditioning	Extinction	Test
OC-OT		10 B: R- 10 C: G-	
NC-OT	10 A: R+ 1 B: ...	10 B: R- 10 C: ...	1 C: R-
OC-NT	1 C: ... 10 D: G+	10 B: ... 10 C: G-	
NC-NT		10 B: ... 10 C: ...	

Note. A, B, C, and D are different galaxies that served as contexts; R (red) and G (green) are sensor lights that may be followed by a spaceship attack (+) or not (-). Numbers refer to the number of trials with each cue. OT = occasion-setting target; NT = no occasion-setting target; OC = occasion-setting context; NC = no occasion-setting context.

in context A, and a green (G) sensor in context D. In phase 2, the target stimulus (R) was extinguished in context B in half of the participants (OT conditions) whereas the other half (NT conditions) were simply exposed to the context. Half of the participants in the OT and NT groups also received extinction of G in context C (OC groups), designed to give it occasion-setting or conditioned-inhibition properties, while the other half had simple context exposure (NC groups). All groups were tested with R in C.

In the OT groups, responding on the test was contrasted against the last extinction trial with R. If extinction endows the test context with negative occasion-setting properties, suppression ratios should be higher (i.e., less expectation) in the OC-OT group than in the NC-OT group, where renewal should be observed. In the conditions where the target was not extinguished (the NT conditions), suppression in the test was contrasted against the last conditioning trial from phase 1. Strong suppression was expected in the NT-NC condition as it assessed the effect of a context change on a simple excitator. However, if extinction in C endowed C with inhibitory properties, less suppression should occur in the OC-NT group.

Method

Participants. Counterbalancing, described below, required a minimum of 64 participants (16 per group). A total of 135 volunteers participated in the experiment. Of those, we analyzed the first 128 to maintain equal weighting among the balancing factors. The experiment had a power of .976 to detect a large effect, and .89 to detect an intermediate-large effect. Seventy-one university-student volunteers were from the United States and 64 were obtained from Spain in the same way as in previous experiments.

Apparatus. Participants in the United States played the game in Dell laptop computers in separate rooms. The video game was viewed on 35.56-cm (14-in) laptop monitors (30.5 cm × 19 cm W/H). The resolution was set to 800 × 600 pixels and 24-bit color depth. Participants in Spain played the game on Dell desktop computers with 22-in monitors. These were not isolated by the trapezoidal boxes as in previous experiments, but were placed in 1.5 × 1.5-m square cubicles that contained a table, a chair, and the computer.

The video game, thoroughly described in Nelson and Sanjuan (2006), simulated as if the participant was inside of a spaceship. Its view (see Nelson & Sanjuan, 2006, Figure 1) contained an window (23.5 × 14 cm) embedded in a metallic frame (the control panel). The control panel had a row of five black horizontally aligned circles (3.28 cm diameter each) just below the window. The sensor light was presented in the middle circle and consisted on a 5-s illumination of this oval. Its color could be red or green.

Four different background galaxies (Hubble telescope photos of different Nebulae) could be displayed through the window to be used as contexts. One was a predominately blue image of the Pillars of Creation area of the Eagle 1 nebula referred to as "EAGLE_NABULAE," a second one predominately red image of the Crab Nebula referred to as "CRAB GALAXY," a third one ("SWIRL GALAXY") displayed a scene with brightly colored blobs (Swirl Nebula), and the fourth ("MAGELLAN GALAXY") was a predominately yellow nebulae (Magellan nebulae). Context switches were advised as explained in Nelson and Sanjuan (2006). Briefly, a standard Microsoft Windows message box informed

them that "You, your sensors, and the enemy are being transported to (name of the galaxy) for further testing. Press OK to proceed." After clicking they were transported to a different galaxy. The CRAB and MAGELLAN galaxies served as contexts A and D. Contexts B and C were the other two, counterbalanced.

The spaceship flew through the galaxies in a randomly determined path. The participant's mouse clicks resulted in a torpedo being fired on a variable-ratio 3 schedule. The enemy spacecraft was hit by the torpedoes in a random half of those firings, resulting in a point being added to a counter placed at the middle-top of the window frame. The spaceship was not destroyed but continued flying throughout the game.

On a conditioning trial, the sensor was illuminated for 5 s. After its offset, a round green torpedo ("US") exploded in the center of the screen and the message "Power at ___ percent. Controls frozen for ___ seconds" appeared. The message was present until power was 100% and seconds 0, and the participant could not fire any torpedo during that time. The numbers in the blanks were determined by dividing the number of clicks during the sensor by that number plus the average rate mouse clicks in the 5s stimulus presentations across the game. The resulting ratio was then multiplied by 120. The result was that, the more they suppressed their responding during the sensor, the less time their controls would be frozen.

Procedure. The 64 conditions required for grouping (four groups) and counterbalancing (16 sub groups), described below, were randomly assigned to participants without replacement to ensure that every condition contained two subjects (one in each condition in each country).

Once sat at the computer desk, the participants read the instructions and then listened while the researcher read them aloud. The instructions informed them that they were to play a video game where they had to earn points by shooting torpedoes at a spaceship by clicking the mouse. They were instructed that the spaceship may attack them and drain their power, leaving them unable to play until their power was recharged. They were told that attacks were unavoidable, but that, if they believe they could be attacked, they could prepare by suppressing their firing to conserve power and recover from the attack quickly. They were also informed that sensors would appear and be useful for them, without any further indication. Once ready, they pressed the "s" key of the keyboard to begin the experiment.

In conditioning participants received 10 reinforced trials with a red (R) sensor in context A and 10 with a green one (G) in context D. These were divided into two main blocks of 10 trials each, which were further divided into subblocks of five. The first subblock contained five trials in one context (A:R+ or D:G+), the second had five trials in the other context, with the order counterbalanced within blocks (e.g., Block 1 = 5A:R+, 5D:G+ or 5D:G+, 5A:R+). The order of the trials was the same in the second main block of 10. Additionally, they received 40-s of exposure to either Context C or B (counterbalanced) between Trials 3 and 4 of the first subblock, and 40-s exposure to the alternate context between Trials 3 and 4 of the second subblock.

In phase 2, participants received two alternations of five trials in one context followed by five trials in the other context. The OT conditions had extinction of R in context B, whereas the NT conditions had equal exposure to the context. Participants in the OC conditions received extinction of G in context C, whereas

those in the NC conditions received equal exposure to the context. The order in which conditioning occurred (ADAD or DADA) was balanced against the order of exposure to the extinction contexts in phase 1 (BC or CB), which was also balanced against the contexts order during extinction (BC or CB). That, combined with the physical counterbalancing of the identity of contexts B and C resulted in 16 conditions per group. The intertrial interval (ITI) was variable and averaged 11 s. On test, participants were transported to context C and, 11 s later, the Red sensor appeared and was not followed by an attack.

Data analysis. Computer collected the number of mouse clicks made 5-s prior to the CS (PRE) and during the CS. These data were transformed into standard suppression ratios [CS/(PRE + CS)] for analysis. Data were analyzed as in the prior experiments. Any differences that might exist between the Spanish and American samples would be confounded with the differences in the apparatus used and, thus, the nationality of the participants was not included in the analysis.

Results

Overall, conditioning and extinction (not shown in a figure) progressed as expected. Suppression was acquired to both R and G. Trials \times OStarget (OT vs. NT) \times OSctxt (OC vs. NC) ANOVAS on each cue showed effects of Trials, $F_s(9,1116) \geq 25.4$, $ps < .0001$, $\eta_p^2 \geq .17_{(.13-.2)}$, $MSE_{range} = 0.012-0.015$, with no reliable effects involving the grouping variables ($ps > .05$). Suppression ratios decreased (i.e., suppression increased) from Trial 1 ($\bar{x} = 0.24$) to the last trial ($\bar{x} = .099$).

During extinction of G, suppression decreased from a mean ratio of 0.11 (first trial) to 0.45 (last trial). A Trials \times OStarget (OT vs. NT) ANOVA revealed an effect of Trials, $F(9, 558) = 35.25$, $p < .0001$, $\eta_p^2 = .36_{(.3-.4)}$, $MSE = 0.02$, with no other effects, $ps > .5$. The Trials \times OSctxt (OC vs. NC) analysis of extinction of R also revealed an effect of Trials, $F(9, 558) = 51.92$, $p < .0001$, $\eta_p^2 = .46_{(.39-.49)}$, $MSE = 0.017$, and no interaction with OSctxt

$F(9, 558) = 1.41$, $MSE = 0.017$, but there was a small overall effect of the OSctxt variable, $F(1, 62) = 4.14$, $p = .046$, $\eta_p^2 = .06_{(.0005-.18)}$, $MSE = 0.13$, which indicates that levels of extinction of R were slightly lower in the OC-OT group ($\bar{x} = .33$), which also had extinction of G, than in group NC-OT ($\bar{x} = .38$).

The test data are shown in Figure 7. The ratios were inverted (0.5-Ratio) to be consistent with previous figures, where larger numbers indicate a greater response. The left of the figure, above *Suppression*, shows the final extinction trial with R (E10) in the OT groups or the last conditioning trial (C10) in the NT groups, and the responses at test. The data above *Test—Last training trial*, shows the difference between the test and the last training trial (i.e., the effect of the context change).

Suppression ratios were analyzed with a Trials (last training vs. test) \times OStarget (OT vs. NT) \times OSctxt (OC vs. NC) ANOVA. There were main effects of Trials and OStarget, but also a super-seding Trial \times OStarget interaction, $F(1, 124) = 36.47$, $p < .0001$, $\eta_p^2 = .22_{(.13-.33)}$, $MSE = 0.015$. There was also a reliable OStarget \times OSctxt interaction, $F(1, 124) = 4.25$, $p = .04$, $\eta_p^2 = .033_{(.0007-.099)}$, $MSE = 0.024$, reflecting a greater overall difference between the NC/OC conditions within the OT groups than in the NT groups (see analysis below). There was no Trial \times OSctxt interaction, which would be expected if the contexts generally

Figure 7. Results of Experiment 4. Left panel: mean inverted suppression ratios in the last conditioning trial (C10) or extinction trial (E10) with cue R, and responses at test. Right panel: performance at test minus in the last training trial (either C10 or E10). Vertical bars represent the standard error of the mean. OT = occasion-setting target; NT = no occasion-setting target; OC = occasion-setting context; NC = no occasion-setting context.

acted as conditioned inhibitors, $F < 1$, $P_{HO/D} = .91$. Neither was the Trial \times OStarget \times OSctxt interaction reliable, which would be expected if the contexts only acted as occasion setters, $F < 1$, $P_{HO/D} = .90$.

Considering the Trials \times OStarget interaction, we would expect the effect of Trials to differ in the two OStarget conditions. As shown in the figure, the interaction is clearly attributable to a small decrease in suppression in the NT groups and a large increase in the OT groups. There was an OSctxt \times OStarget interaction, shown above, suggesting that the effect of OSctxt differs between that the two OStarget groups, but is the same at both the last trial of training and the test. Trials \times OSctxt ANOVAs conducted within each OStarget group confirmed those descriptions. Comparing OC-OT and NC-OT groups, revealed a strong renewal to R as shown in the effect of Trials, $F(1, 62) = 33.96$, $p < .001$, $\eta_p^2 = .35_{(.20-.48)}$, $MSE = .017$, and no interaction with whether extinction of G had occurred in the context or not, $F(1, 62) = .017$, $p = .9$, $P_{HO/D} = .89$, $MSE = .02$. The main effect of OSctxt only approached reliability, $F(1, 62) = 3.69$, $p = .05$, $\eta_p^2 = .06_{(.000001-.16)}$, $MSE = .03$, reflecting what was shown in the extinction analysis. Extinction of R was somewhat less effective in the OC-OT condition, than in the NC-OT group. The same analysis in the NT conditions showed a small effect of Trials, $F(1, 62) = 4.145$, $p = .046$, $\eta_p^2 = .06_{(.002-.182)}$, $MSE = .01$ as there was a small loss of suppression between the last trial of conditioning and the test, and no interaction with the context treatment, $F(1, 62) = 1.22$, $p = .27$, $\eta_p^2 = .019_{(.000001-.106)}$, $P_{HO/D} = .81$, $MSE = .01$. As in Exp. 3, the small loss in the NT condition indicates that we were not so far into a response ceiling as to be unable to detect an effect of the context manipulation. There was no evidence of contextual inhibition. The main effect of OSctxt was not reliable, $F < 1$.

Discussion

Using a conditioned suppression task (Nelson & Sanjuan, 2006) we investigated whether the contexts can function as either conditioned inhibitors or negative occasion setters. Two groups were simply conditioned with the target cue in a context before they

were tested in a different context. Suppression transferred equally to the new context regardless of whether the context had prior extinction of another cue within it or not. The extinction context did not acquire inhibitory properties, replicating Nelson et al. (2011) results.

An ABC renewal design was used in other two groups. Suppression responses renewed after extinction with a context change. Importantly, the amount of renewal did not differ depending on whether the test context had been trained as a possible negative occasion setter or not. The results were fully consistent with the prior experiments presented here.

Meta-Analysis

Data from all experiments were combined for analysis. We used the last trial of extinction and the test trial data from the OC-OT and NC-OT conditions from each experiment. Inverted suppression ratios from Exp. 4 were used to keep all effects in the same direction. Within each experiment, the data from those trials were converted to Z scores. Then, the last trial was subtracted from the test trial to represent the level of renewal in each experiment. Those renewal data were analyzed with an Experiment \times Context Type (neutral or occasion-setting) ANOVA.

As indicated by the intercept, the mean level of recovery ($Z = 1.17$) was clearly above zero, $F(1, 231) = 222, p < .0001, \eta_p^2 = .49_{(.42-.55)}, MSE = 1.20$ (as a between-subjects factorial, MSE was 1.20 for all tests in the overall ANOVA). As we suspected, renewal

vary slightly, $\eta_p^2 = .06_{(.011-.101)}$, by Experiment, $F(3, 231) = 4.54, p = .004, \eta_p^2 = .06_{(.01-.1)}$. The effect in each experiment, represented by the difference in Z scores from testing to training was 1.01, 1.37, 1.44, and 0.84, for Exps. 1–4, respectively. From those scores it appears that the effect in Exps. 2 and 3, which did not differ from each other, $F < 1$, was larger than that observed in Exps. 1 and 4, which also did not differ, $F < 1$. The effect in Exp. 3 was greater than in both Exps. 1, $F(1, 144) = 5.24, p = .02, \eta_p^2 = .035_{(.002-.096)}, MSE = 1.15$ and 4, $F(1, 158) = 12.61, p = .0005, \eta_p^2 = .07_{(.02-.15)}, MSE = 1.10$, yet that observed in Exp. 2 was only greater than in Exp. 4, $F(1, 91) = 4.25, p = .04, \eta_p^2 = .04_{(.001-.13)}, MSE = 1.25$, not differing from Exp. 1, $F_s = 1.57, p = .21, MSE = 1.35$.

Of most interest for the present article, there was a power of .99998 to detect a large effect and 0.97 to detect a medium effect. The analysis revealed no effect of Context Type, $F(1, 231) = .07, p = .79, \eta_p^2 = .0003_{(.0000004-.012)}, MSE = 1.20, P_{H_0/D} = .94$. The mean recovery score for those tested in a neutral context was 1.146, while for those being tested in a potentially occasion-setting context was 1.188. The lack of difference was the case for each experiment, as indicated by the lack of an Experiment \times Context Type interaction, $F(3, 231) = .35, p = .18, \eta_p^2 = .005_{(.0000004-.015)}, MSE = 1.20, P_{H_0/D} = .9995$.

The data supported the null hypothesis, $P_{H_0/D} = .94$, leaving only weak support for any alternative ($P_{H_A/D} = .06$). Of those alternatives (OC < NC, OCX NC), only one has any consistency with an occasion-setting account (i.e., OC < NC). The other result does not support occasion-setting transfer, leading the data to provide fairly strong support ($p = .97$) against extinction endowing the contexts with the transfer properties of occasion setters. The same set of transformations and analyses were applied to the NC-NT and OC-NT conditions of Exps. 2–4 that tested for

inhibition. The intercept was not significant, $F(1, 191) = 1.51, p = .19, MSE = 1.08$, showing that, collapsed over the experiments, there was no effect of context change. However, there was an effect of Experiment, $F(2, 191) = 3.11, p = .047, \eta_p^2 = .03_{(.00002-.032)}$, Exps. 2 ($Z = .03$) and 3 ($Z = .05$) did not differ, $F < 1$. Exp. 4 ($Z = -.33$) showed more effect of change than Exps. 2 and 3 combined, $F(1, 195) = 6.26, p = .01, \eta_p^2 = .03_{(.004-.032)}, MSE = 1.07$.

Of most importance, there was no evidence of context inhibition. The analysis had a power of .9998 and .936 to detect a large or medium effect, respectively. The analysis showed no effect of Group, $F(1, 191) = 0.46, p = .498, \eta_p^2 = .002$, and supported the null $P_{H_0/D} = .92$. There was no interaction with Experiment, $F(2, 191) = .66, p = .52, \eta_p^2 = .007, P_{H_0/D} = 0.99$. As with the occasion-setting analysis, only one pattern of results in favor of an alternative would be consistent with a conditioned inhibition account, raising the support for no transfer of inhibition to .96. These results do not necessarily imply that inhibition cannot develop to a context. Exps. 2 and 3 were intentionally designed to minimize that possibility by including reinforced filler trials in the extinction context. However, Exp. 4 did not include such trials. Nevertheless, as intended, these experiments demonstrate that renewal can and does occur in the absence of contextual inhibition.

General Discussion

The renewal effect indicates that the CS and the extinction context both need to be present for extinction learning to be expressed. In explaining that necessity, it has been widely assumed that the extinction context functions as a negative occasion setter (e.g., Bouton, 1993, 2004); the context sets the occasion for the CS to be nonreinforced. In Bouton's (1993; see also Bouton & Nelson, 1994) terms, the context does so by enabling an inhibitory association learned in extinction that counters the excitatory association acquired during conditioning.

To understand whether contexts act as negative occasion setters we tested them for one of the apparent characteristics of these type of stimuli. Unlike a conditioned inhibitor, a negative occasion setter does not affect responding to a simple excitator, but it will suppress responding to a target of a different FN discrimination (Holland, 1989b; Lamarre & Holland, 1987; Swartzentruber, 1995; Wilson & Pearce, 1990). Therefore, an extinction context should be able to reduce renewal to any other extinguished CS. Two prior attempts to demonstrate this property, however, either found no transfer (Todd, 2013) or cannot rule out a conditioned-inhibition account (Swartzentruber, 1993).

Four experiments addressed this question in human participants. Exps. 1 through 3 used a predictive learning task, and Exps. 4 used a behavioral suppression task. All four tested a presumably occasion-setting target (i.e., an extinguished CS) within a context trained as a negative occasion setter (i.e., has had extinction of another CS within it) in an ABC renewal design. Exps. 2 through 4 also explored the conditioned inhibitory properties of the extinction context by testing a nonextinguished cue in a context where extinction took place. None of the experiments provided evidence for any type of transfer. Combining the data across experiments provided strong support for that null effect.

The results regarding whether conditioned inhibition accrued to the extinction contexts are consistent with prior findings (e.g.,

Baker et al., 2012; Bouton & King, 1983; Bouton & Swartzentruber, 1986, 1989; Grahame et al., 1990; Nelson et al., 2011). That failure was intentional in Exps. 1 through 3, as we included manipulations which should reduce the likelihood of the contexts acquiring condition inhibition. That was not the case of Exps. 4. Nevertheless, the strong suppression established at the end of training, and the small generalization decrement observed with a switch to a neutral context, might have limited our abilities to observe conditioned inhibition.

The results regarding an occasion-setting interpretation are consistent with those found by Todd (2013) with an instrumental procedure. They are also consistent with Miller et al. (2020) who found no evidence of transfer when conditioned inhibition accrued to the extinction context had supposedly been eliminated. In that experiment rats received conditioning with CSs X and Y in different contexts. Then, X was extinguished in context B and Y in context D, using short 6-s ITIs. Next, two main groups were formed where the rats had 12-hr of exposure to the test contexts (B, C, D) or not. On test, X was turned on immediately upon placement of the rat in the contexts. Renewal occurred in both groups when tested in the neutral context C. However, only the group that had received 12-hr exposure to context D showed renewal in that context. In the absence of such exposure to context D, its effect on extinction performance, acquired during extinction of Y, appeared to transfer to X. The authors suggested that context D functioned as a conditioned inhibitor, and that the exposure extinguished that inhibition (see also Polack et al., 2012). Thus, in the absence of conditioned inhibition, where transfer might be attributed to occasion-setting, no transfer occurred. Of interest, the same extinction-of-inhibition treatment applied to Context B did not lead to a recovery of responding to X.

If selective transfer is an inherent property of occasion setters, then either failures of transfer suggest that extinction contexts do not act as occasion setters, or there are yet-to-be-determined parameters of the situation that prohibit transfer from occurring. Holland's (1983, 1985) original proposal for occasion-setting did not predict transfer. Rather, occasion setters were assumed to operate on particular CS-US units, which would appear consistent with our findings. Nevertheless, emerging examples of transfer led Holland to modify his approach into one involving multiple memory systems. Here, serial FN discriminations would result in the formation of higher order CS-US control units upon which the occasion setter would act. Holland (1989b, 1992; Lamarre & Holland, 1987) contended that transfer to other targets would be possible only if those targets were also represented in the high-order system by way of having been involved in another discrimination. In our experiments, the extinction contexts and the extinguished CSs should be represented in the same level of a hierarchical system and transfer should have occurred.

Selective transfer is also present in the model of occasion-setting offered by Schmajuk, Lamoureux, and Holland (1998). Their computational model consists of learning direct associations between stimuli and outcomes, as well as indirect associations that are mediated by a layer of hidden units that learn by way of backpropagation. Through the use of select learning-rate parameters and a unique set of initial starting weights (see Appendix B, p. 35 of Schmajuk et al., 1998), occasion-setting discriminations are solved through the layer of hidden units, whereas simple CS-US associations are acquired through the direct connections. Because

the hidden layer is shared by all stimuli participating in such discriminations, transfer will occur between them but not affect simple excitors whose associations are stored more so as direct connections. Thus, if occasion-setting occurred in our experiments, selective transfer by way of the hidden units should be observed. If occasion-setting did not occur yet renewal was observed, then the representation of the US would have to be suppressed by a direct context-outcome inhibitory association and conditioned inhibition should be detectable. That is, in cases where renewal is observed, then some form of transfer should also be observed. This latter statement is also true of Rescorla's (1985) idea that negative occasion setters raise a threshold for activation of the US representation. Because the mode of operation is on the outcome representation, transfer is expected between any stimuli which are predictive of the same outcome.

Selective-looking transfer could also arise from generalization. Holland (1989b, pp. 324–325) acknowledged that “participation of cues in like occasion-setting functions might render them more similar,” and that there is “little to distinguish this possibility from the view that transfer is greater within than between systems.” This view was also considered by Bonardi (1998). She contended that occasion setters act on the target-US association and thus, do not generally transfer to other stimuli. However, training the two targets in similar discriminations should produce acquired equivalence between them (Bonardi & Hall, 1994; Honey & Hall, 1989). As the transfer targets and contexts in our experiments were treated identically, some equivalence should have been established between them and transfer should be observed.

Generalization-based transfer can also be expected on the basis of Pearce's (1987) configural model. According to this model entire configural patterns of stimulation get associated with the US or its absence. For instance, in our designs extinction of Y in context B would result in a configural BY compound acquiring a CS—no-US association, and responding to Y in context C at test would depend on its similarity to BY. Importantly, less responding (i.e., transfer) would be expected in the experimental groups which also received extinction of X in C, because in those groups inhibition would generalize to CY from both BY and CX.

In Pearce's terms, our failures of transfer would be explained by our contexts having very low salience across all variations on those stimuli across experiments. In Exp. 1, the context was physically much like the target cue. It only differed from it in that it was present also during the presentation of the outcome. In Exp. 2 and 3 the context was considerably different from the cue, being represented by a larger background image. Again, it was present in both the cue and outcome screen. Finally, in Exp. 4 the context was represented by a large image upon which all elements of the method were presented. In this case, the context was present not only during the cue and outcome presentation, but persisted through the ITI. Thus, the lack of transfer we observed does not appear to be idiosyncratic to a particular set of experimental parameters regarding contexts.

Occasion-setting transfer appears to be a relatively reliable phenomenon. Although transfer is seldom complete, it does occur when the stimuli have been involved in identical discriminations, or even similar ones where a negative occasion setter affects the target from a conditioned-inhibition discrimination (Lamarre & Holland, 1987). We are aware of no demonstrations of a failure of transfer between occasion setters when training has been arranged

to promote it and the discriminations have been well learned. Holland (1989b) has shown transfer when the occasion setter, CS, and US have all been involved in occasion-setting relationships, even though the particular CS-US combination being tested had never been occasion set. For instance, where “+” and “!” represent different appetitive USs, rats learned $A+/X \rightarrow A-$ and $B!/Y \rightarrow B-$ discriminations. Then, A was paired with ! and testing revealed that X modulated the newly acquired !-based responding. That is, X transferred its power to a particular CS-US combination that, itself, had never been occasion set.

Larrauri and Schmajuk (2008) applied the Schmajuk, Lam, and Gray (1996) model to renewal and explained the effect without recourse to occasion-setting. The model works by way of a complex interplay of contextual inhibition and attention variables. In addition to predicting a forthcoming stimulus (e.g., a US), the model functions as an autoencoder and must predict the stimuli that are input to it at any point in time. The degree of error that is produced in that net prediction is interpreted as “novelty” detection, which then boosts attention to the stimuli. During extinction, excitatory CS-US associations will decrease, but that will be offset by a “protection from extinction” (Rescorla, 2003) mechanism as inhibition of the outcome will accrue to the context. Moreover, the CS and extinction context come to predict each other while CS-conditioning context associations are extinguished. As the environment comes to be correctly represented, there will be a decline in attention to both the CS and the extinction context. When the CS is tested then in the conditioning context, it is released from any influence of inhibition that the extinction context might control. According to Larrauri and Schmajuk, the model also predicts that novelty and attention are lower during extinction than conditioning because “CSs and CXs can predict themselves and each other, and, therefore perfectly match predicted and actual values” (Larrauri & Schmajuk, 2008, p. 645), whereas USs are less perfectly predictable and novelty is better maintained during conditioning. Thus, not only is the CS released from some inhibition, its representation is boosted by the better-maintained novelty in the conditioning context.

Although the extinction context is said to acquire inhibition, the model predicts that it will fail a summation test (i.e., not produce transfer) because attention to the context is too low to adequately express its inhibition against a strong, well-attended CS. Novelty and attention are, according to the model, low in contexts where extinction has occurred. Thus, extinction of another CS in the test context will reduce the novelty and attention of that context just as extinction of the test CS reduced that of the training context. An extinction treatment of another CS in the test context should eliminate renewal (see Larrauri & Schmajuk, 2008, p. 656). The novel presence of the test CS in the test context should increase novelty and attention, but the effect would be more evident on the following trial and should result in the expression of that context’s inhibition, also eliminating renewal. In our experimental groups the test and extinction contexts received the exact same treatment, thus the contexts should have acquired identical properties and been largely interchangeable. Moreover, the use of reinforced filler trials during extinction should serve to better maintain attention to the contexts and help ensure that any inhibition accrued to the contexts is expressed at test.

A more recent extension of the Schmajuk et al. (1996) model involves the addition of a layer of “configural” units through

which learning might also occur, as well as through the originally proposed direct connections (Kutlu & Schmajuk, 2012). These units are hard-wired through random nonmodifiable connections to the inputs so that they code for different combinations. That is, a single configural unit can be active for different combinations of input units. Thus, when these configural units are used, some degree of transfer between different stimuli and stimulus combinations can be expected, although it depends on the randomness of the initial connections. The attention that these units receive is affected by novelty (based on errors in prediction), but with a much greater threshold for error than for the simple inputs themselves. Thus, attention increases only when the model fails to correctly predict outcomes over many trials, biasing the system to use those units when the constraints of the training problem do not allow it to be solved by CS-US associations, such as in negative patterning (i.e., $A+/B+/AB-$). Regardless of the amount of transfer that might be allowed by the random connections to configural units, there is little need for these units to be engaged. As shown by Larrauri and Schmajuk (2008), the linear aspect of the model is sufficient to find a solution to the renewal problem by making the extinction context inhibitory. It is only after training, and the failure of summation tests, that it is revealed that a nonlinear solution was used.

Other accounts of renewal have also been proposed, which would not predict transfer, and are therefore consistent with our results. A problem with these accounts is that they are inferred by eliminating other possible mechanisms, as opposed to generating a positive prediction apart from the result that they explain. Bouton’s (1993) initial proposal regarding extinction and renewal was that input from an extinguished CS and the context converged on an Estes (1976)-type “AND” gate, which was in turn responsible for activating inhibition to reduce the outcome expectation. Such a mechanism, by itself, does not imply that transfer should be observed (see also Bouton & Nelson, 1994, for a discussion of transfer within Bouton’s, 1993 framework). Miller et al. (2020), discussed earlier, offer the idea that extinction results in the context acquiring conditioned inhibition that is “stimulus specific.” Such a proposal is isomorphic to Bouton’s use of an “AND” gate. Rather than viewing the inhibition acquired in extinction as a context-dependent property of the extinguished CS, Miller et al. (2020) view the acquired inhibition as a stimulus-specific property of the context of extinction. We presently imagine no way to distinguish between these possibilities, nor any way to positively test these ideas.

The accounts of Bouton (1993) and Miller et al. (2020) are also generally parallel to “unique cue” approaches (e.g., Rescorla & Wagner, 1972; Wagner & Brandon, 2001) or the activation of “peripheral units” as described by McLaren and Mackintosh (2002). In such frameworks the CS and contexts combine to form a unique stimulus that would be responsible for the control and expression of inhibition. That particular cue would simply be absent whenever the CS-Context combination used in extinction is absent, and no transfer would be expected. As noted by McConnell and Miller (2014), a unique-cue approach requires the assumption that such cues are more present in extinction than conditioning, as is the case with Bouton’s initial theorizing.

The present results reinforce what is shown generally by the renewal effect. That is, extinction performance relies on a particular combination of extinguished CSs and their contexts. More-

over, the reliance appears to be more specific than what might be assumed based on an occasion-setting account. Transfer between extinguished CSs and contexts does not appear to be a necessary requirement for the presence of the mechanism. Pavlov (1927) initially proposed that extinction was the result of a change in the cortical representation of the CS. Though largely ignored in present theory (but see Robbins, 1990) this proposal is in line with the present data, which point to extinction resulting in changes in how the CS is represented whereby it may be represented jointly with the context as a unique cue, or as a configural cue with limited generalization.

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